

LINGUOCOGNITIVE AND NATIONAL-CULTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF CONSENSUS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17618916>

Muminov Sidikjon Mirsobirovich

Professor of the Department of Linguistics of FerSU,

Doctor of Philological Sciences

siddiqjon.mominov@bk.ru

+998904062729

Kodirova Munisabonu Ibrokhimjon kizi

Researcher of Fergana State University

munirasattorova879@gmail.com : 91-113-71-31

ABSTRACT: *This article analyzes the linguo-cognitive and cultural aspects of the concept of “consensus” in English and Uzbek. It explores the conceptual frameworks formed around the term, the language units associated with it, and how these reflect the worldview, social values, and communicative norms of each culture. The comparative analysis highlights how the idea of social agreement and unity, as expressed by “consensus,” is represented and perceived in both linguistic and cultural contexts.*

KEYWORDS: *consensus, linguo-cognitive analysis, cultural-specific features, conceptual analysis, intercultural communication, language and cognition, social agreement.*

ENTRANCE

Achieving consensus in Uzbek society is based on the principles of verbal agreement, consultation with elders, respect, and collective decision-making.

The main features include the following. Verbal agreement is considered important in Uzbek culture. In most cases, contracts and documents are of secondary importance. The reason for this is the strong mutual trust between people. The opinion of the elderly and adults always prevails. Advice from elders and respected individuals will be a

key factor in achieving consensus. Collective unity and solidarity also play an important role. In Uzbek culture, peaceful resolution of conflicts is considered preferable.

In English culture, the achievement of consensus is carried out on the basis of communication, compromise, legal agreements, and written contracts. In its main features, it differs significantly from Uzbek culture. Written documents and formal agreements are more important in English culture than verbal agreements. Any agreement is confirmed by specific

documents. Dialogue and diplomacy are priorities. Conflicts are resolved through discussion. Individual and collective rights have their own balance in English culture. The opinion of each person is taken into account separately.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The concept of consensus has been widely studied in linguistics, philosophy, sociology, and cultural studies, and is interpreted more as a process of agreement, solidarity, and reaching a common decision in the social environment. In Western scientific literature (Habermas, 1990; Rawls, 1993) consensus is viewed as the central category of social agreement and communicative communication. In English, this concept is often expressed through synonymous units such as agreement, harmony, mutual understanding, and is actively used to express social cooperation.

In Uzbek linguistics, the concept of "consensus" is more associated with the processes of social unity, consultation, and agreement (Karimov, 2016; Zhuraev, 2020). In studies in the national-cultural context, this concept is inextricably linked with the ancient traditions of consultation, the culture of collective decision-making and cooperation of the Uzbek people.

On the linguocognitive approach (Kubryakova, 2004; Lakoff & Johnson, 2003) the concept of consensus is considered as a cognitive model in human thinking and worldview. This makes it

possible to analyze it not only through language, but also through national mentality and cultural values.

Thus, the analysis of the available literature shows that the expression of the concept of consensus in English and Uzbek has both commonalities and differences. These differences are mainly manifested in cultural context, social values, and linguocognitive models.

Methodology

1. This research is based on linguocognitive and linguocultural approaches. It includes the following steps:

2. Conceptual analysis - units expressing the concept of "consensus" in English and Uzbek (lexical units, phraseological combinations, metaphorical expressions) are identified.

3. Corpus analysis - the frequency of use and contextual features of speech samples reflecting the concept of consensus from English and Uzbek text corpora are studied.

4. Building a cognitive model - conceptual metaphors and symbolic models formed on the basis of the concept are identified (for example, models such as "consensus - bridge," "consensus - unity," "consensus - road").

5. Cultural-comparative analysis - the connection of the concept of consensus with national-cultural values in English and Uzbek is studied.

6. Concluding generalization - the common and different aspects of the concept of consensus in two languages and cultures are determined.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The concept of consensus is linguistically expressed differently in different languages. The linguistic features of the concept of consensus in English and Uzbek can be as follows. Consensus in English: Differences in terminology and forms of expression. In English, consensus is often expressed by the word "consensus." This word can mean both joint agreement and a common opinion or decision. Contextual usage: There are expressions such as "A consensus opinion," "reach a consensus," "build a consensus." This means that in the process of achieving a unified group decision, all parties take into account each other's opinions. The use of the word consensus in grammar. The word "consensus" is used in English as an uncountable name. It is used as follows: "The consensus is...," "There is a consensus on...," "We reached a consensus on...." Rules for using the word consensus in pragmatics. In the English language, the pragmatic features of the concept of consensus depend on many factors, among which social context, relationships between people participating in communication, and the purposeful use of language play an important role. Below are the pragmatic features of the concept of consensus in the English language. 1. Dependence on context. The concept of consensus is usually used in the process of discussion between groups or communities. For this, context is very important. For example, policies and decisions: Used to achieve

consensus between political parties or government agencies, in developing an important law or political decision. Research and scientific fields: In scientific communities, consensus is often used to make decisions based on a scientific approach or results. 2. Balance and reaching agreement. Consensus mainly refers to the process of reaching mutual agreement and satisfying all participants. This often requires achieving a balance between several parties or opinions. In English, expressions such as "reach a consensus" or "build a consensus" are often used to describe this process. Examples: "The committee reached a consensus after several hours of discussion." "We need to build consensus on the new policy." 3. Coordination and conditions. Achieving consensus is often based on all parties listening to each other's opinions, coordinating, and agreeing on certain terms. In English, the words expressing this process are used together with such words as "compromise" and "agreement." This indicates the need to agree on conditions, opinions, and decisions during the discussion process. 4. Social role and etiquette. In the English language, the concept of consensus also depends on social ethics and the role of the persons participating in communication. For example: in a corporate or political context: It is required to reach consensus in order to maintain equality or balance between the persons participating in the dialogue. Obtaining consensus here depends on social norms and the fairness

of the discussion. In small groups and family contexts: Achieving consensus is often based on cooperation and close relationships. For example, achieving consensus in decision-making within a family or small group is usually aimed at ensuring loyalty and respect. 5. Social force and manipulation. Sometimes the process of achieving consensus can also be associated with social force or manipulation. In this case, the process of obtaining consensus may be aimed at giving preference to the opinion of some persons or at adapting others to their opinion. Such pragmatic features often arise for political or commercial purposes.

Language and intonation. In the process of achieving consensus, it is necessary to pay attention to the intonation of the English language and the subtexts of the language. For example, phrases like "I think we might have reached a consensus" or "I believe we are getting close to a consensus" give a slightly positive connotation, which indicates a successful discussion process. On the other hand, expressions such as "There is a consensus, but it's not quite final yet" may mean that a mutual agreement has not yet been reached. From a pragmatic point of view, the concept of consensus in English depends on groups, social etiquette, the nature of the discussion process, as well as the relationships between participants, and is expressed through the contextual use of the language and configuration changes. This concept implies social agreements,

coordination, and fair decision-making. The pragmatic aspect of consensus in English is that this concept is often used at the end of a discussion or decision-making process, for example, in a political or organizational setting.

RESULT

The use of consensus in Uzbek differs slightly from English. 1. Terminology and forms of expression: In the Uzbek language, the word "consensus" is used in various forms, but this concept is sometimes expressed by terms such as "agreement," "mutual exchange of opinions," or "joint decision-making." Contextual usage: used in expressions such as "achieving consensus," "jointly reaching consensus," "mutual agreement." 2. Grammar: In the Uzbek language, the word consensus is usually used as a collective noun. Phrases such as "achieving consensus," "coming to consensus," "being in consensus" are often used. 3. Pragmatics: the pragmatic features of the concept of consensus in the Uzbek language also depend on the social and communicative context of the language, as well as on the relationships and purposes of communication between participants.

The pragmatic features of the concept of consensus in the Uzbek language can be analyzed as follows. 1. Dependence on context. In the Uzbek language, consensus is often used in a social, political, or business context. In politics and society: achieving consensus is often used between different political forces or in making important decisions

in society. This means mutual agreement and joint decisions. Research and scientific fields: The concept of consensus in the Uzbek language also refers to the unification between scientific thoughts and approaches in the scientific environment. 2. Agreement and balance. Achieving consensus means ensuring mutual agreement and balance. In the Uzbek language, this process is often expressed by such expressions as "to reach an agreement," "to make a joint decision." These expressions require the exchange of ideas and joint decision-making among all members of the group. Examples: "All parties reached an agreement." "First of all, we need to reach a consensus." Social etiquette and role. In the Uzbek language, the concept of consensus can be related to social etiquette and the roles of individuals. For example: In family and small groups: In the Uzbek language, consensus is often focused on ensuring respect and solidarity between participants in decision-making within the family or small group. In the corporate context: Achieving consensus at the workplace, especially between managers and employees, often requires cooperation and maintaining balance. Demonstrative and expressive forms of language. In the Uzbek language, the concept of consensus is often expressed by such expressions as "achieving consensus," "reaching an agreement together," "being in consensus." These expressions, depending on the pragmatic context of the language, signify agreement and ensure that they

correspond to the opinions of the parties involved in the communication. Subjective approach and manipulation. In some cases, the process of achieving consensus can be associated with social or political manipulation. This means that one party may try to impose its interests on others. This pragmatic aspect is more common in politics and business. Example: "Some parties are acting on their own interests in achieving consensus." Intonation and emphasis. In the Uzbek language, intonation also plays an important role in expressing the concept of consensus. The statement "We have reached a consensus" may indicate strong confidence and success, but the statement "We are trying to reach a consensus" indicates that a final agreement has not yet been reached. Through this intonation, it is possible to convey information about the social situation and the level of discussion in communication. Use of formal and informal language. In the Uzbek language, the concept of consensus differs in formal and informal communication. In a formal context, for example, in political or business meetings, consensus is expressed more clearly and firmly: "We have reached a consensus." In the informal context, this concept is expressed more softly and freely: "We agreed," "Well, shall we do this?"

In the Uzbek language, the pragmatic features of the concept of consensus differ depending on the social and cultural context, as well as the

purpose and roles of the participants in communication. This concept is often aimed at ensuring agreement, balance, and cooperation, but in some cases may also relate to social or political manipulation. Through the grammatical and pragmatic aspects of language, different forms and uses of consensus are distinguished. In the Uzbek language, the pragmatic aspect of consensus is also related to the processes of discussion or

decision-making, expressing the exchange of ideas and agreement between groups.

The English word "consensus" and the Uzbek word "consensus" are very similar, but their usage differs depending on the specific grammatical and pragmatic features of the language. In the Uzbek language, this concept is often expressed differently or used in conjunction with other terms.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Boboxonov U. Til va madaniyat: lingvokulturologik tadqiqot. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston, 2008.
2. Duranti A. Linguistic Anthropology. – Cambridge University Press. 2007.
3. Jo‘rayev R. Diplomatiq muomala va muzokaralar etiketi. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2012.
4. Mamatov A. Til va jamiyat: kommunikativ aspekt. – Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2018.
5. Nemetskaya T.A. Kognitivnaya lingvistika: osnovy i perspektivy. – M.: Flinta, 2010.
6. Nurmonov A. Til – tafakkur – madaniyat. – Toshkent: Akademnashr. 2008.
7. Searle J.R. The Construction of Social Reality. New York: Free Press. 1995.
8. Sharifov Sh. Milliy tafakkur va til konseptlari. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2016.
9. Wierzbicka A. Understanding Cultures through Their Key Words. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997.
10. Yuldasheva D.A. Konseptlar lingvokulturologik talqinda. Samarqand: SamDU nashriyoti, 2020.